

Influence of Silane Coupling Agents on Interlaminar Fracture in Glass Fiber Fabric Reinforced Unsaturated Polyester Laminates

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Abstract

The relationship between the adhesive properties of the inter-phase of glass fiber/resin and the resultant composite Mode I delamination fracture toughness in glass fiber fabric laminate (GFFL) was studied. The Mode I interlaminar fracture toughness of GFFL was obtained by using Double Cantilever Beam (DCB) specimen. The delamination resistance of GFFLs which have two silane coupling agents and several concentrations finishes was discussed on the basis of interlaminar fracture toughness. The crack propagation behavior was mainly divided into stable and unstable manners. The fracture toughness and stability of crack propagation were dependent on the types of silane coupling agents and their concentrations.

1 Introduction

Glass fiber fabrics are used for printed circuit boards as the materials of reinforcement and insulation. The very important properties such as heat resistance, dimensional stability, resin impregnation, and others need to be improved more and more today. Especially, the heat resistance is the most important property which determines the performance of printed circuit boards. Silane coupling agents are finished on glass fiber fabrics in order to obtain good heat resistance of printed circuit boards. A silane coupling agent is an adhesive material which is like a bridge between glass fiber and matrix.

The heat resistance of laminate is greatly influenced by silane coupling agents [1]. We often use "pressure cooker test" [1],[2], which is one of the typical industrial tests for heat resistance to evaluate the performance of printed circuit boards. This test is valuable in predicting whether laminates can withstand the introduced humidity during the process of manufacturing printed circuit boards. Penetration of water into the interfacial region can be accelerated by boiling the coupons in a pressure cooker, and observed by immersing the boiled coupons in molten solder. Since water suddenly converts to steam through the heat of molten solder, it may be observed visually that delamination occurs. Judging from this test, we can estimate the heat resistance of the glass fiber fabric laminates. The measurement which can rate the delamination resistance at the numerical value has not been developed yet.

The mechanical property and heat resistance of GFFL composite are influenced by the adhesive property of glass/matrix interphase. Crick et al. suggests that the interlaminar fracture morphology of carbon fiber/PEEK interphase can be examined by using Mode I (DCB) [3]. Since the crack propagation behavior of DCB test is similar to the growth of the delamination of the GFFL in the pressure cooker test, fracture toughness values can be used as a simulation for the delamination. The observation of the crack propagation during DCB tests is also important to evaluate the delamination.

The goal of this research has been to understand the relationship between the interfacial adhesive properties of silane coupling agent and the resultant mode I delamination fracture toughness. Interlaminar fracture toughness test of GFFL was carried out in order to evaluate the delamination resistance of GFFL. Mode I interlaminar fracture toughness of glass fiber fabric laminates finished two silane coupling agents and three concentrations was measured. The crack propagations of GFFLs were mainly divided into two types when DCB test was carried out.

2 Experimental

2-1 Materials and specimens

The vinyl ester resin (Ripoxy R-806B) for matrix is a type of unsaturated polyester resin and was purchased from Showa High Polymer Company. The plain E-glass fiber fabric (WE18W 44x34 count/inch) was supplied by Nitto Boseki Company. The fibers from the fabric have a diameter of nine microns. Both MPS (γ -methacryloxypropyltrimethoxy-silane:A-174) and GPS (γ -glycidoxypropyltrimethoxysilane:A-187) purchased from Nippon Unicar Company were used as silane coupling agents. MPS has an organic function which can react with the double bond of vinyl ester resin: GPS, on the other hand, has no double bond of its molecular structure. The aqueous solution of silane coupling agents were acidified with acetic acid at pH 4.0. Glass fiber fabrics were dipped into the silane aqueous solutions of 0.01, 0.4, 1.0wt%

MPS, and 0.4wt% GPS. They were squeezed by squeeze rolls and dried at 110°C for 10 minutes.

Figure 1 illustrates the schematic diagram of the glass fiber fabric laminate for DCB specimens. The laminates were consisted of matrix (vinylester resin polymerized with 0.7wt% methyl-ethyl-ketone-peroxide) and plain glass fiber fabric. 20 plies laminate was consolidated for 48 hours at room temperature by handlay-up method for DCB testing and 8 plies laminate was also consolidated for DMS testing. Each sample volume fraction was about 44%. PTFE 40 μm thick film was inserted on the midplane as a starter slit during fabrication shown in Figure 1. The specimens were cut into pieces approximately 100mm long, 25mm wide, and 4mm thick in a rectangular fixture parallel to the weft glass fiber strand shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Schematic diagram of the glass fiber fabric laminate for DCB specimen.

Figure 2 DCB specimen geometry and test setup.

2-2 Fracture toughness test

Figure 2 illustrates a DCB specimen geometry and test setup. The specimens were loaded at the crosshead rate of 1.0mm/minute using Instron 4206. The crack propagation length was measured on the specimen both sides by using two traveling microscopes. The specimens were loaded continuously up to get 10mm increment of crack length. And then specimens were unloaded. This procedure was continued as above until specimens were split into two parts.

2-3 Data analysis of interlaminar fracture toughness

G_I value is calculated as follows:

$$G_I = \frac{P^2}{2B} \times \frac{d\lambda}{da} \quad (1)$$

(where P=load, B=specimen width, a=crack length, λ =compliance)

The value of the interlaminar fracture toughness, G_I was calculated using Kageyama's analytical compliance method [4].

$$a/H = A_1 \lambda^{1/3} + A_0 \quad (2)$$

(where H=half length of specimen thickness)

The slope of the line is A_1 and the value of G_I is then determined as:

$$G_I = \frac{3P_c \lambda^{2/3}}{2A_1 B H} \quad (3)$$

(where P_c = critical load)

Figure 3 Relation between cubic root of compliance.

Figure 3 illustrates the relation between the normalized crack length and the compliance of 0.4wt% GPS laminate to obtain A_1 value according to equation (2). Figure 3 indicates that the equation (2) can be applied to calculating fracture toughness because the fit of the data to the straight line is quite excellent. Figure 3 is a representative of all samples for this condition. The other figures have the similar straight slope as the Figure 3. Equation (2) can determine A_1 value.

2-4 The fracture toughness of the vinylester resin

The fracture toughness of the vinylester resin was measured by using of compact specimen (ASTM E 399-83).

2-5 Tensile, flexural, and interlaminar shear strength

The GFFLs were cut and tested in tensile, flexural, and interlaminar shear in accordance with ASTM Standard D-3039, D-790, and D-2344, respectively.

Table 1 Mechanical properties of specimens.

	Epoxy Silane		Methacryl Silane	
	0.4wt%	0.01wt%	0.4wt%	1.0wt%
Tensile Strength (MPa)	361	341	373	371
Young's Modulus (GPa)	21.7	23.4	22.4	22.1
Flexural Strength (MPa)	421	447	461	460
Interlaminar Shear Strength (MPa)	(29.6)	(39.4)	(48.9)	(47.8)

3 Results and Discussion

3-1 Tensile and flexural test of GFFL

The results of tensile and flexural strength tests are summarized in Table 1. The results of the tensile strength data in Table 1 indicates that 0.01wt% MPS specimen has the lowest strength. The specimens of 0.4 and 1.0wt% MPS have the almost same tensile strength. The Young's modulus of four specimens data in Table 1 also have the nearly same modulus value. Table 1 shows that the flexural strength and interlaminar shear strength of 0.4wt% GPS specimen is lowest. Both of 0.4 and 1.0wt% MPS specimens show the strongest data.

The results from Table 1 do not present the difference between the adhesive interphase of 0.4 and 1.0wt% MPS specimens. The tensile, flexural and interlaminar shear strength test are not enough sensitive to examine the interfacial adhesive strength of 0.4 and 1.0wt% MPS surface finished GFFLs.

3-2 Fracture toughness test

Figure 4 (a)-(d) show the load-displacement curves for four different silane finished laminates. The chart pattern of Figure 4 (a) is roughly the same as that of Figure 4 (b). The load-displacement curves in Figure 4 (a) and (b) are smoother than those in Figure 4 (c) and (d). These four figures can be divided into two patterns in terms of crack propagation behavior: one is a stable crack propagating growth pattern, the other is an unstable crack propagating growth pattern[3]. A stable crack propagation shown in Figure 4 (a) and (b) grew slowly during the crack propagation. During the measurements of the crack propagation in 0.4 and 1.0wt% MPS specimens, the crack started to grow slowly from starter defect (initiation) and kept growing slowly a couple of times (stable crack propagation). An unstable crack suddenly occurred fast in the specimen of 0.4 and 1.0wt% MPS and both the stable and unstable crack propagation were seen in the same specimen. The specimen of 1.0wt% MPS was split at less than 20mm displacement distance. The 1.0wt% MPS specimen was easy to make unstable propagation and it's propagating was too fast to stop. The values of fracture toughness in Figure 4 (a) and (b) scattered widely. However, the unstable crack in Figure 4 (c) and (d) propagated fast and did not scatter widely and the crack run in the more brittle area, which was hardened by MPS, than that of Figure 4 (a) and (b).

Figure 4 Load-displacement curves for (a)0.4wt% epoxy silane, (b)0.01wt% methacryl silane, (c)0.4wt% methacryl silane, and (d)1.0wt% methacryl silane finished GFFLs.

3-3 Macroscopic and microscopic observation of fracture surfaces

Figure 5 (a)-(d) show the macroscopic photographs of the fracture surfaces of four specimens. The light region corresponds to the stable crack propagation. The dark region corresponds to unstable crack propagation. Because the crack propagation grew across the glass fiber fabric, the stable light fracture surface in the both sides of GPS finished laminate of Figure 5-(a) is seen like several ribbons running to the crack direction. The whole area in Figure 5-(b) became white. The one side of Figure 5-(b) upper picture is covered with vinyl ester resin. On the contrary the other side is covered with glass fiber fabric. The stable and unstable crack propagation are seen in the same sample of both 0.4wt% MPS and 1.0wt% specimens. The white glass fiber area in MPS 1.0wt% is smaller than that of 0.4wt% MPS. Thus unstable crack propagation in 1.0wt% MPS occurred more possibly than that in 0.4wt% MPS.

(a) Epoxy Silane 0.4wt%

(b) Methacryl Silane 0.01wt%

Stable Fracture

(c) Methacryl Silane 0.4wt%

(d) Methacryl Silane 1.0wt%

Stable Fracture

Unstable Fracture

Figure 5 Macroscopic observation of fracture surface for (a)0.4wt% epoxy silane, (b)0.01wt% methacryl silane, (c)0.4wt% methacryl silane, and (d)1.0wt% methacryl silane finished GFFLs.

Figure 6 (a) and (b) show the scanning electron micrographs of fracture surfaces for DCB specimens. Figure 6 (a) shows the stable crack growth of 0.4wt% epoxy silane finished specimen. This figure shows the exposed glass fibers with no resin. Figure 6 (b) shows the unstable crack growth of 0.4wt% methacryl silane finished specimen. The fracture surface is covered with resin and more than several spotted glass fibers. It can be concluded that the stable crack propagate through the interphase of glass/resin and the unstable crack propagates through the resin between glass fiber fabrics.

3-4 Relation between fracture toughness and crack length

Figure 7 (a)-(d) illustrates the relation between fracture toughness, G_I and the crack length for four types of surface finished laminates. Figure 7 (a)-(d) correspond to the load-displacement curves in Figure 4 (a)-(d). Figure 7 (a) and (b) show that the fracture toughness of the stable crack propagation is almost constant.

Figure 6 Scanning electron micrographs of the DCB specimen fracture surfaces. (a) stable crack growth of 0.4wt% epoxy silane finished specimen, (b) unstable crack growth of 0.4wt% methacryl silane finished specimen.

Figure 7 Relation between fracture toughness (G_{IC}) and crack length for (a) 0.4wt% epoxy silane, (b) 0.01wt% methacryl silane, (c) 0.4wt% methacryl silane, and (d) 1.0wt% methacryl silane finished GFFLs.

On the other hand, Figure 7 (c) indicates high fracture toughness. The unstable crack gives low values of fracture toughness and the stable crack gives high values. Thus the result shows the range of fracture toughness is wide. The fracture toughness at $a/H = 10-20$ (normalized crack length) is rather lower than that at $a/H = 20-30$ in Figure 7 (d).

3-5 Fracture toughness of three categories: (i) initiation; (ii) stable crack propagation; (iii) unstable crack propagation

We divided the crack propagation behavior into three categories as shown in Figure 8 : (i) initiation; (ii) stable crack propagation; (iii) unstable crack propagation.

The mean values of five specimens for each category for four types of laminates are plotted in Figure 9.

(i) Initiation of crack propagation:

Fracture toughness of MPS finished GFFL is decreasing in proportion to the MPS concentration. Since the adhesive property of glass fiber/vinylester resin interphase at 0.01wt% MPS GFFL is insufficient, the crack started to grow from the space between PTFE film/resin and the crack propagated along the glass fiber/resin interphase. Fracture energy was dispersed through this poor adhesive 0.01wt% MPS glass/resin interphase. Thus the higher initial toughness at 0.01wt% MPS GFFL was obtained. For the case of the 0.4 and 1.0wt%

Figure 8 Schematic of crack growth pattern division on load-displacement response.

Figure 9 Fracture toughness of four surface finished GFFLs considering crack propagation pattern.

MPS finished glass fibers, the crack started from the space between PTFE film/resin and propagated into resin rich region between glass fiber fabrics because the bond at the interphase is strong. The fracture toughness of these two concentration specimens was close to that of the polymerized vinyl ester resin.

(ii) Stable crack propagation:

The 0.4wt% MPS specimen indicates the highest fracture toughness in Figure 9.

(iii) Unstable crack propagation:

The fracture toughness decreased in proportion to the MPS aqueous concentration.

The 0.4wt% GPS specimen has the lowest value of all four specimens in the initiation and stable fracture because GPS has no organic function which can react with vinyl ester resin.

This phenomena indicates that the excessive amount of MPS may cause the unstable crack propagation around glass fiber. As the interphase between glass and vinyl ester in 1.0wt% MPS is too strong, the

crack grows easily into the rich resin region. For the case of unstable fracture toughness, the unstable fracture toughness decreases in proportion to MPS aqueous concentration in Figure 9. The interlaminar fracture toughness is very much dependent on silane type (organic function of silane) and its concentration. Moreover optimum silane amount on glass fiber should be tailored to increase the delamination resistance of GFFL.

4 Conclusions

1. Fracture toughness test by using DCB specimen gives the sensitive analytical technique to evaluate the very slight surface finish difference on the glass fiber fabric laminate.

2. Interlaminar fracture toughness of GFFL is influenced by silane type and silane solution concentration. There is the optimum amount of silane on glass fiber to accomplish the maximum of fracture toughness. The reduction of fracture toughness of GFFL was observed with excessive amount of silane.

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